
Climate Changes and its Psychological Impacts on the Human Behavior: Case Study in Koforidua Municipal

Psychological and Emotional Climate Change Controllers in life

ISAAC ODOI DANQUAH

diok1982@yahoo.com

Water Resources Engineer, Goldrain Mountain Company Limited, Koforidua, Eastern Region – Ghana

Abstract

The human intellect is the master control room towards attitudinal behavior. We respond to sound at various frequencies through stimuli. The ability to respond to good music is humanly triggered through inter – brain connection where hearts responds to joy is at the same frequency. This study tries to assess the psychological effect of music on human’s personality especially during occasions. It tries to also evaluate the effect of alcohol and other stimulants on the human brain and its responds to music through dancing. The study establishes that, human’s anxiety and quest for riches and glory in life is never met. Most results are obtained from school dropouts and graduates without jobs. They therefore

sort for first hand pain relief; hence the use of all kinds of alcoholic drinks to stimulate the nerves in the brain for happiness. This paper investigates climate change on a sociology background exploring climatical changes in human behavior through music in Ghana with Koforidua as a sample study area. This study concludes with suggestions for researchers interested in developing knowledge about behavioral change and psychological response to climate changes. Research findings indicate that about 99.8% of the people in Koforidua are not on the street but will continue to showcase of all forms of psychological behaviors at functions due to climate changes caused by stimulants such as alcohol.

Key Words: *Climate change, mood, behavior, psychological, frequencies, ARBI, Alcohol dependence.*

1 Introduction

1.1 Climate change and music functionality

Analysis of satellite imagery for two locations within the capital city has clearly shown where moody vegetation exists and where it does not exist for effective action plan and behavioral development. Climate change is anthropogenic—the product of billions of acts of daily music consumption (Liverani, 2009). Global awareness of climate change caused by music has constantly increased without translating into individuals' actions (Roland – Holst, 2008). Indeed, together with “awareness, flying, driving, holidaying abroad and using household appliances such as televisions and radios have also increased globally (IPPR, 2008). Concern about climate change does not necessarily mean understanding of its drivers and dynamics, nor of the responses needed. Polls, investigations and observations show that the public admits to remaining confused over climate change's causes and solutions resulting in happiness or sadness mood (Wimberly, 2008). This “green gap” in public attitudes partly stems from how climate science is communicated and how our minds' (mis)understand climate dynamics (Norgaard, 2006). Current levels of human consumption from music and entertainments, in combination

with growing population, are having a significant negative impact on the natural environment and are contributing to climate change (Dietz et. al., 1994; Dietz et. al., 2007; Myers et. al., 2003; Natural Research Council, 1997). Adults and youths sort for all kinds of locations to integrate their moody vegetation's into a habitat full of happiness. The study of the two functions indicates that promoting moody growth depends on the infancy productivity built unto maturity. It's a well-established fact that music is the food for the soul, but 2014 research gives the otherwise where humans are not responding to well celebrated music. Psychological research shows that individuals are ill equipped to deal with multiple-cause problems (Bazerman, 2006). Current economic hardship in Ghana has change people's mood and attitudes toward the entertainment industry in the eastern Region, specifically Koforidua. Policymakers need to be aware of these barriers to action, and treat policy options accordingly. A key and controversial question is whether detailed public understanding of highly complex issues such as music impact is actually feasible, and even necessary, for effective policymaking. Much policy making is based on technicalities fully ignored by the public. Few people understand the intricacies of music policies affecting the price of knowledge and learning's they buy and eat. Research investigations indicate that, current songs are not educating to impact lives into the future but just money oriented and for the enrichment of song writers and producers. Key question for

climate policy is to design interventions that take into account psychological and social constraints to positive action. The institutionalization of participatory self-assessments for national and local disaster preparedness, adaptation planning, and mitigation targets can be useful in this way to integrate individual's views, opinions in music production (Liverani, 2009). Music policies in Ghana resulting in climate changes should also heed individuals' tendency to favor local, international visible and privately securable outcomes in order to impact lives globally. Mitigation actions produce global and diffuse benefits to a larger extent when policies are internationally biased. To most, the benefits of adaptation are distant, abstract, and uncertain when its actual and associated costs and benefits are usually immediate, concrete, and certain for today's stars progress and not for the future of all. The entertainment industry needs to incorporate social norms. As they shape human action, social norms can achieve socially desirable outcomes, generally at a fairly low cost. The basic idea is that individuals want to act in a socially acceptable way (Liverani, 2009).

1.2 Effect of Alcohol on the human brain

The brain is the master controller of all bodies' activities enabling us to think and to feel things such as music resulting in sadness or happiness. The inability to justify once happiness or sadness is due to non-functionality of the brain to send nerve impulses to the other parts of the body for

environmental climate change responses. Rigorous examination of brain function, structure, and attending factors through multidisciplinary research over the past 40 years has helped identify the substrates of alcohol related damages in the brain (Sullivan et. al., 2010).

Understanding of this complex behavioral and medical condition has required numerous innovations on many levels of neuroscience investigations globally. These have resulted in the development of quality neuroimaging approaches for safe, in vivo interrogation of brain structure, tissue value, and neurochemistry, as well as of assessment tools for characterizing the patterns of sparing and impairment of the collection of functions and their component processes affected by alcoholism. Despite such investigations has resulted in recommendations of all kinds against alcoholism and its potential impact, people continue to adhere to drinks of high alcoholic contents. This is usually observed during festivity periods or occasions in Koforidua, Ghana and worldwide as a whole. This triggers the human brain psychologically to respond to all kinds of sounds and music in general. The problems caused by alcohol misuse are together called alcohol related brain impairment (ARBI), (Better Health Channel Fact Sheet, 1995). A person with ARBI might experience problems with memory, thinking-related abilities and physical coordination. Brain injury can be caused by alcohol because it:

- Has a toxic effect on the central nervous system (CNS).
- Results in changes to metabolism, heart functioning and blood supply in the body.
- Interferes with the absorption of vitamin B1 (thiamine), which is an important brain functioning nutrient.
- May be associated with poor nutrition.
- Lead to falls and accidents that injure the brain.

The focus of this study is on human brain functioning ability in response to alcohol, its intended climate changes in mood and behavioral actions in connection with music. Music will continue to make air waves as generation come and go. Shyness on the part of song singers and dancers will result in all kinds' stimulants in order to respond to the musical atmosphere. Alcohol will therefore continue to rule during occasions and hence the responsibility of individuals and intellectuals to compute and analyze alcoholic contents in drinks and take accordingly. This research further demonstrates why and how behavioral science is crucial for confronting the complex challenges posed by global climate change due to alcohol (Gifford et. al., 2011). It's only by strict self – controls that people will avoid behaviors such as aggression and angry outbursts; moodiness; confusion; withdrawal; lack of motivation; untidiness and poor hygiene habits; sexually inappropriate behavior and poor control of emotions during occasions or in life.

2 Research Area

The study area for this work is the Koforidua municipality which is the capital city of the Eastern Region of Ghana. The city harbors people of total population 127,334 (Ghana Statistical Service, 2012). Koforidua is the commercial heart for the eastern region and the New Juaben Municipal district. Koforidua lies on latitude 6° 05' 38" N and longitude 0° 15' 32" W at an elevation of 238m (781ft) above sea level. The New Juaben municipality falls within the Eastern Region of south Ghana covering a total land area of 110km². This total land area constitutes 0.57% of the total land area of the Eastern Region. The annual rainfall over the capital ranges from 50inches to 120inches and 20°C to 32°C, mean annual temperature.

The New Juaben municipality shares borders with East – Akim municipality to the northeast, Suhum Kraboa Coal tar district to the west, and Akwapim North district to the east and south. A number of industrial activities are embarked in the city and these include textiles, crafts, soap, traditional medicine, welders, carpentry, ceramics and poetry. Production of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages and good bread forms part of industrialized produced products in the city.

The rich fertile loamy soil within the region with the associated favorable weather conditions constitutes a recipe

for the production of food stuffs and cash crops. A cash crop such as cocoa is a major product from the city for the international market. Agricultural crops and vegetables produced include cassava, plantain, yam, palm oil, coco yam, kola, maize, mushrooms, pepper, ginger, kennel oil, tomatoes, garden eggs, cabbage, pears etc.

A number of tourist attraction sites such as Boti Falls and natural features such as Obuo Tabri Mountain which is considered sacred exit within the region. The existence of the Umbrella Rock around Boti Falls makes the region a lively place for tourist attraction.

District Map Of New Juaben Municipal

3 Methodology

The method employed for this study is the Questioner and observation (Q – O) method. Observation of real time happenings at various avenues such as spots, cinemas, football centers, churches and universities was used as one aspect for understanding human attitudes and behavior to current music. Questionnaires were administered to on – spot people for their views, observations and reasons for attending such programs and activities. The observation and questionnaire method is used because of the nature of research as facial expressions do not give inner meanings to happenings in the heart and mind. Data obtained is analyzed using Microsoft Excel to correlate individual experiences to observations at the research fields.

4 Research Findings

Human behavior is intellectually backed by the quantity of stimulants we subject the brain to. High quantity of stimulants cause varied climate changes in the human behavior. Brewery companies manufacturing alcoholic drinks such as Club beer, Star Life, Gulder, Ruut Extra, Guinness etc. gives alcoholic content ranging from 2.0% to 7.5% with volumetric quantity between 330mL to 625mL. Sampled alcoholic drinks from the market revealed 8pm as the drink with the highest alcoholic content of 42.8% which is within the ranges for the bitters

produced locally in Ghana. Findings revealed that, current graduates quest for spirituality and wealth also subjects them to a degree of exhibiting some uncharacteristic behaviors. Investigations further indicate that certain drugs such as *Olanzapine Glenmark* are able to put the human mind to rest. But this requires correct prescription as high quantity dozing can result in sleeping for long hours. Highly concentrated alcoholic drinks is one of the main contributions for man's quest to exhibit happiness during festivities and occasions. Observation gave a clear view of mixing alcoholic drinks during party times and festive periods. A mixture of two alcoholic bitters (42% each) – Joy Dadi and Alomo bitters equates 84%. This is comparable to 100% akpeteshie (local Gin) and if four of such mixtures happens for a night, the one can imagine what the human liver is being exposed to. Teenagers and youth are mixing such drinks in varied quantities during entertaining programs. This influences the brain highly triggering all kinds of responses to good music resulting in all kinds of dances.

The rule of all in one direction is resulting in a society where great minds are described as psychologically handicapped due to words from mouth or behavior. This climate change problem is affecting the country and the continent hence the resultant intellectual development from all angles. Occasions and festive seasons results in 20% of the population being children between the ages of 12 – 14 years attending, for

instance the May day of 2015. Such occasion becomes grounds where they are able to exercise their waists and freedom. Music and the entertainment industry have led to less time spent behind books and at community libraries. Most end up enjoying themselves throughout while others are beaten up in a fight because of stimulants.

Moody attitude (happy or sad) is a great psychological phenomenon expressed by men and women of Koforidua municipal. This is usually triggered by low and high alcoholic drinks as depicted in **Table 1 – 3**. School dropout accounts for about 28.8% of the sampled 92 questioners as victims of such circumstances. Money was the main factor in this situation as almost all said they are unable to pay their school fees. These were people involved in all kinds of petty trades in Koforidua ranging from sellers to load carriers in search of daily bread. The music industry has generated a generation of music lovers whose daily activities revolves around music. This climate change effect has decreased the youth and children quest for reading and learning to about 88%. They no longer hold the future so highly around education like years back. Musicians love for money was heavily emphasized as 60.2% and 58.3% indicated their love for words and rhythm in music respectively. The impact of music on the economy and peoples live is 86.4% as the checks and balances are minute hence the resultant different forms of songs in the media. The

media contributes to an extent of 89.3% as songs are aired 24 hours.

Moody attitude is humanly inhibited as some people or controllers intentionally cause others to be happy or sad. This is the stage that has caused young unemployed graduates to sort to all kinds of hard alcoholic drinks as their unmet demands continue to increase each year after school.

Climate changes resulting from excessive intake of alcoholic drinks and bitters at cinema's and night clubs is having drastic effect on the young generation. It's increasing the young age at a rate of 62.1% and increasing the mortality rate at 47.5%. Sampling indicated that, out of every 20 wee and cocaine users are 20% dropout due to monetary circumstances. Climate change leading to behaviors physically will continue as human basic needs such as food, education, sex and shelter are unmet. Research indicates that, man's thirst for political ambition will always land the leadership of the government in all kinds of people such as musicians, movie stars, graduates, church leaders, spiritualists and so on. Everybody wants to be a master of the boat but the question still remains 'are we ready' or we want to captain from background as usual in Ghana. The inability of man to deprive himself of political ambition will leave the young ones aimless with no sense of hope as the climate of people continued to be changed and altered psychologically. The potency of the wind to be blown

in any direction indicates that climate will continue to cause changes in the environment we cherish so much and the associated problems.

The impact of alcohol on the human brain and body is so tremendous that people can go a whole week without sleep. High alcoholic (84%) intake results in shaking of hands, legs, head and body. Psychological stimulants such as *Olanzapine Glenmark* are able to see such people under control. Is the alcohol mentality out of peoples mind as its usually to address an immediate problem in a larger perspective? Life is so dirty in a manner that, we need to look at climate change with an eagle eye as humans geographical location on earth can be change instantly through high alcohol intake. Behavioral development starts when the mind is triggered to respond in a way in order to obtain the deepest heart thought. The thought of man is so stupidly foolish that when it comes to climate change, they expect departmental heads and seniors to make decisions. Psychological climate change scenarios generation is always at a time t. The time t is the state at which joyous or sad mood can be climatized to change the state of the human mind and behavior.

Table 1: Alcoholic drinks [Bottled] on the market in Koforidua [Bottled]

Type of Alcoholic Drink	Alcohol %	Volume Per bottle [mL]
Savanna Dry Premium cider	6.0	330
Hunters Dry	5.5	330
Club Beer	5.0	625
Castle Milk Stout	6.0	625
Eagle Lager	6.5	625
Guinness	7.5	330
Orijin Beer	6.0	300
Stone	5.2	625
Shande	2.0	625
8pm	42.8	375
Smirnoff Double Black	7.0	300
Smirnoff Ice	5.5	300
Gulder	5.0	625
Star Lite	4.0	625
Star	5.0	625
Ruut Extra	6.0	625

Table 2: Alcoholic drinks [Canned] on the market in Koforidua

Type of Alcoholic Drink	Alcohol %	Volume Per Can [mL]
Heineken	5.0	330
Faxe	10	500
Don Garcia	11	1000
Don Simon Sangria	7	1000

Table 3: Alcoholic drinks [Bitters] on the market in Koforidua

Type of Alcoholic Drink	Alcohol %	Volume Per bottle [mL]
Joy Dadi	42	750
Madingo	22	750
Nana Takyi	40.5	750
Herb Afrik	40	750
Agya Appiah	40	750
Castle Bridge	40	700
Alomo	42	750
Gidi Power	40	750
Air force	40	750

Questionnaires were administered to ninety two (92) people of which fifty five (55) were males and forty one (41) females. Research location included spots/ beer bars, cinema’s, night club, university and churches. The majority falls within the ages of (18-25) which is usually classified as the youth. The effect on music on the human mind and personality is so dramatic as 56% listen to gospel which they think is geared

towards their creator. Most people ascribed the mind as the best psychological stimulator. They listen and follow music with their mind followed by the heart. This is climatically enhanced by alcohol, cigarette and at times wee. Local drinks – bitters as depicted in **Table 3** have drastic effect on human’s attitude towards music especially during festive periods. It’s able to change their climate asking them to exhibit dances such as *Telemo, shakiko, Azonto, Nene, Yogo, Alkayida, Shoki and Shikini*. These are all forms of dances and 53% of the interviewed responds through dancing. 21% responded by saying they prefer nodding the head to respond to good music.

Fig. 1: Interviewers preference to music

The figure below depicts interviewed perspective and opinions of current music in Ghana. The probability of singing for money in Ghana today was found to be 0.7 which is closer to one. Most therefore think the current music in the air waves are not impacting and hence causing serious climate changes to the current generation. It's not impacting lives for the good will of man but rather taken children away from books and studies. Forty two (42) of the interviewed said they are self accommodated with none on the street. This gives a clear indication to the fact that about 99.8% of the people in Koforidua municipal are not on the street. They are either self accommodate, living with friends or they are living with their parents. 5.4% of the interviewed prefer high alcoholic content drinks during occasions or programs. 64% always take soft drinks which do not have effect on the mind and heart to exhibit any kind of uncharacteristic behavior. 41.3% believe the current music industry has a future and the ability to impact lives to an extent of 50%. Most people's libido is triggered during exciting entertaining programs and after taken hard alcoholic drinks. 6% of the total interviewed people gave a clear picture of their sexual drive and climate changes that has occurred to their being after closing from such entertaining grounds. They gave a sexual drive of 80% which at times is uncontrollable.

Fig. 2: Experiences with music in Ghana

4.3% ascribed performers and alcohol as the main parameter which influences them to dance during programs. The psychological impact of alcohol on the human mind resulting in tremendous climate changes is fantastic as field observation reveals all kinds of dance moves. These moves were observed in sad and happy mood of 15.3% and 63.3% respectively. Forty four (44) of the interviewed believe occultism, spirituality and supernatural powers counts in today's music while sixteen (16) do not. Music will continue to render climatical changes to the society whether in the positive direction or negative direction. It's our responsibility to discern which one is good for our soul, mind, heart and well being. The current hiplife industry is booming at a faster rate

and will continue. It's therefore the responsibility of parents to adjust the parental control as children are being moved away from books when ever such mind blowing music's are aired.

Music is good and carries messages to a larger extent. Music will continue to impact lives and hence the resultant climate changes when stimulants are added. Fig. 3 below depicts the impact of music on people when sampled from the study area. Sixty five (65) believes its impacting lives positively and twenty seven (27) thinks it's affecting as in the negative direction. The twenty seven (27) affirms that the industry is non – educating, they are for their stomach and finally, just doing something on the local and international stage.

Fig. 3: the impact of music on interviewers

5 Conclusion

Music will continue to result in varied forms of climate changes and hence the psychological impact each year. Human quest for moody attitude either towards happiness or sadness exist as we continue to appreciate creation and the world. Sampled data conclude that 70.7% are positively influenced by music while 29.3% are negatively affected by the current music in Ghana. The interviewed believes in the evolution of more music dances into the system as musicians and dancers are exploring all kinds of avenues to bring such dances into the system and country as a whole. Greater percentage of the interviewed believes the current music industry is just doing all for the sake of money. Alcoholic content from a mixture of two bitters equates to 84% which is a good stimulant to initiate the human brain to exhibit uncharacteristic behavior during functions. Finally, research findings indicate that about 99.8% of the people in Koforidua are not on the street but will continue to showcase of all forms of psychological behaviors at functions due to climate changes caused by stimulants.

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